

Investigation of Adhesive Bond Strength of Fire-Resistant Thermal Insulation Composite Geopolymer Material made of Construction and Demolition Waste

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Abstract. This research paper focuses on assessing the adhesive bond strength of an innovative fire-resistant thermal insulation composite material developed from geopolymer composites. The novel geopolymer composite material is derived from the alkali activation of recycled ceramic waste tiles. The study evaluated the effectiveness of the bond strength between these distinct geopolymer samples by examining the mechanical properties of geopolymer samples after post-curing and exposure to high temperatures of 800°C and 1050°C.

The results indicate that both post-cured geopolymer samples and those subjected to elevated temperatures met the minimum mechanical properties requirements expected for a composite material. Post-curing samples exhibited an average density of 887 kg/m³ and a compressive strength of 9.4 MPa, while samples exposed to temperatures of 800°C and 1050°C showed average densities and compressive strengths of 896 kg/m³, 12.9 MPa, and 853 kg/m³, 10.2 MPa, respectively. The bond between the distinct geopolymer samples within the composite material demonstrated exceptional adhesion.

Even after exposure to prototype samples to elevated temperatures of 800°C and 1050°C, the fire-resistant (compact) and thermal insulating (foamed) geopolymer samples retained their strong bond. However, it was observed that a minor failure occurred within the foamed section. Isolating the foam section revealed significantly low to nearly non-existent compressive strength. Notably, this structural weakness did not compromise the overall integrity of the bond formed between the two geopolymer samples.

Keywords: *Bond Strength, Thermal Insulation, Fire Resistance, Geopolymer, Elevated Temperature*

1. Introduction

The adoption of advanced composite materials in structural applications has experienced a significant upswing in the construction sector. These materials, known for their high specific strength, environmental friendliness and enhanced stiffness, empower the production of lightweight and high-performance components for building applications (Shang et al., 2019).

Research has been conducted on the compatibility with various materials, ensuring sufficient interface strength between diverse composites in most practical scenarios. The satisfactory cohesive failure of two diverse geopolymers indicates a full utilization of material strength. Nevertheless, bonded connections of composite materials are highly susceptible to delamination a premature failure mode arising from the elevated peel stress in joint and the comparatively low transverse strength of the composites, leading to fracture between laminate. The results show that maximum joint strength can be achieved when the cohesive failure of the adhesive and the delamination failure of the composite adherends occur at the same time (Kim et al., 2008).

Adhesive bonding stands out as the preferred technique for connecting diverse geopolymer matrix composite materials due to its advantages, providing a lightweight and economical alternative to traditional joining methods like bolting and riveting (Pisharody and Smith, 2022) The techniques traditionally adopted to measure bond strength include pull out test method and assessment of bond strength of composite materials after their exposure to elevated temperature.

Durability is another important and desirable property of hardened geopolymer composite material. Within these composites, an Interfacial Transition Zone (ITZ) emerges as an intermediary region between two discrete geopolymeric components. This ITZ proves to be the weakest link within the geopolymer composite block. Interestingly, when subjected to loads, no microcracks tend to initiate within this region, contrary to expectations. It has been observed that the ITZ in geopolymer composite materials exhibits a reduced microstructural distinctiveness and higher density. High bond strength and tensile strength of the geopolymer composite material is attributed to the robustness of ITZ (Singh et al., 2015).

2. Material and Methods

Alkali activators preparation

The alkaline activator used in this work was prepared by mixing a potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution of 8 M with a sodium silicate solution (MERCK, Na₂O = 8%, SiO₂ = 27%, H₂O = 65% and $d = 1.346$ g/mL). The KOH solution was prepared by dissolving analytical grade anhydrous pellets of potassium hydroxide (MERCK, 99.5% purity) in distilled water and its concentration was kept constant in all the experiments and equal to 8 mol/L (8 M), taking into consideration that at lower alkaline concentrations the content of OH⁻ ions is inadequate to facilitate the dissolution of silicate and aluminate phases and therefore promote geopolymerization (Komnitsas and Zaharaki, 2007). The KOH solution was prepared at least

24 hours before to be used. The optimal solid-to-liquid ratio of the mix design adopted throughout the experiment was 3.4g/mL and for sodium silicate to potassium hydroxide ratio was 1.6 . For the preparation of the foam geopolymers, aluminum powder (Sigma Aldrich, - 325 mesh, 99.5% purity) and Al powder/or hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution (MERCK, 30% wt.) were used as foaming agents.

Preparation of geopolymers

This research introduced two distinct material types: Ceramic Tile Fire-Resistant (CTFR) geopolymer/compact geopolymer and Ceramic Tile Thermal Insulation(CTTI) geopolymer material robust compact geopolymers designed for high compressive strength for use as fire-resistant materials, lightweight foam geopolymers with remarkably low thermal conductivity for application as thermal insulation materials, and composite geopolymers that amalgamated the characteristics of both materials for use in facades.

For the preparation of individual fire-resistant and heat-insulating geopolymer specimens, the alkaline activating solution was blended with the geopolymer precursor (brick waste or ceramic tile waste) in a laboratory mixer for 5 minutes until achieving a homogeneous paste. The resulting paste was then poured into cubic moulds (50 x 50 x 50 mm³) and cured in a laboratory oven under specific temperature and time conditions. In the case of foam geopolymers, a foaming agent was introduced into the paste before moulding and swiftly mixed for an additional 10 seconds. The moulded specimens were left at room temperature for 30 minutes before curing to ensure the completion of the foaming process under mild temperature conditions. Compact geopolymers underwent curing at 50 °C for 5 days, while foam geopolymers were cured at 70 °C for 7 days. After the curing process, geopolymeric specimens were demoulded and allowed to harden at room temperature for 7 days before conducting any tests or measurements.

To prepare the composite geopolymers specimens, the slurry of compact geopolymer was first poured into the molds (50 x 50 x 50 mm³ or 150 x 150 x 50 mm³, depending on the intended test or measurement), forming a 1.5 cm thick layer and then, the slurry of the foam geopolymer was added on top of the compact geopolymer layer, to a thickness of 3.5 cm. Before pouring the foam geopolymer into the molds, the upper surface of compact geopolymer layer was slightly etched, in order to improve materials bonding. The composite geopolymers were cured at 70 °C for 7 days. After curing, specimens of the composite geopolymers were demolded and left at ambient conditions for 7 days before measurements and testing of properties. The composite geopolymers were evaluated in terms of adhesion strength, mechanical strength, and structural integrity after exposure to high temperatures and fire resistance.

3. Results and Conclusion

The assessment of the adhesive strength between the compact and foamed layers in the composite geopolymer involved pull-off adhesion tests conducted in accordance with the EN1542 standard. The specimens for these tests were prisms measuring 150 x 150 x 100 mm³,

comprising a 30 mm thick compact geopolymer layer and a 70 mm thick foamed geopolymer layer. The experimental arrangement for the pull-off adhesion tests and the equipment utilized are depicted in Fig.1

Figure 1. Steps of geopolymer pull-off adhesion testing: (a) drilling of specimens; (b) dollies application and (c) testing equipment and experimental set-up.

Basically, to initiate the test, each specimen was centrally drilled on the surface of the compact layer, forming a core that extended beyond the interface between the compact and foamed layers (Figure 1a). Subsequently, a dolly was securely affixed to the surface of the compact layer using epoxy adhesive (Figure 1b). The pull-off tester was then positioned concentrically over the dolly, as illustrated in Figure 1c. A continuous and uniform load was applied at a rate of 0.05 ± 0.01 MPa/s until the specimen failed. It is noteworthy that, given the manual operation of the pull-off adhesion tester, the operator exercised extra caution to ensure minimal fluctuations in the applied load. This meticulous approach aimed to mitigate potential inconsistencies or variations that could influence the reliability of the results. Maximum of 1.3 MPa interlayer bond strength was also reported (Muthukrishnan, et al., 2021).

Based on the experimental findings, the recorded average compressive strength and bulk density of the compact and foam/ composite geopolymer were 9.4MPa and 889kg/m^3 respectively after curing at 70°C at 7 days, when cured specimens of composite geopolymers were heated at 800°C and 1050°C their mass loss and compressive strength were 1.5% and 12.9MPa at 800°C , and 4.0% and 10.2% at 1050°C respectively. The improvement of mechanical strength at 800°C was attributed by viscous sintering process taken place between the unreacted solid particles and the melted geopolymeric matrix that results in more durable structures (Bajare et al., 2019). Additionally, the thermal stability of compact geopolymers following exposure to high temperatures was assessed. All tests and measurements were performed in triplicate, and mean values, it is evident that the characteristics of the CTFR/CTTI-1 geopolymer composite were notably influenced by the inclusion of the thermal insulation geopolymer, CTTI-1. This is logical given that more than two-thirds of the geopolymer composite comprises this specific geopolymer. Nevertheless, the compressive strength of CTFR/CTTI-1, following both curing and exposure to elevated temperatures, was deemed

suitable for a building façade. This assessment is in comparison to gypsum boards utilized as passive fire protection and thermal insulating building materials, which typically exhibit compressive strengths in the range of 2.4-2.9 MPa, as well as other commercial fire barriers (Sakkas et al., 2013).

The effective bonding between the two distinct geopolymers within the CTFR-CTTI integrated component was further verified through compressive strength testing conducted on samples subjected to temperatures of 800 and 1050 °C. Upon examination of the fragments from the miniature CTFR-CTTI specimens, as depicted in Figure 1, it was evident that the failure occurred within the foam portion. This foam section exhibited exceptionally low to virtually non-existent compressive strength when considered as an isolated material. Remarkably, this structural weakness did not impact the integrity of the bond formed between the two geopolymers. It is noteworthy that the composite geopolymer exhibited high bond strength and tensile strength within the CTFR-CTTI geopolymer material due to robustness of interfacial transition zone (Singh et al., 2015).

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